

SOME COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BENZENE WITH SULPHUR, IODINE, ETC.

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Mechanism of the formation, association and dissociation of the complexes formed between benzene and sulphur or iodine has been investigated from a study of their absorption spectra.

The electrical conductivity of the benzene solution of sulphur or iodine exhibits breaks at 0.54, 0.78 and 1.41% of S and at 0.10, 0.14 and 0.21% of I₂. This brings out the fact that the type of complexes unearthed by the study of the microscopic Raman effect are real. The increase of the conductivity of benzene on the addition of sulphur or iodine shows that some degree of ionisation has been induced therein by these solutes. The purpose of this note is to study the mechanism of the formation, association or dissociation of these complexes from a study of their absorption spectra. The complexes mentioned here may be of the same type as met with in the case of the formation of "lakes" by dyestuff with inorganic salts.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The light from a hydrogen continuum was passed through the benzene or benzene solutions placed in a quartz tube and the photographs of the absorption spectra were taken on panchromatic plates with a Hilger E₁ quartz spectrograph.

The position of the absorption maxima (*m*) and the absorption edges (*e*) are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Temp. 40°.

Absorber.	Absorption edge.	Absorption maxima.	Absorber.	Absorption edge.	Absorption maxima.
Benzene	5852Å	5250Å	Benzene + 0.1% I	5760Å	5250Å
	3260	3180			3960
	3080	3020	Benzene + 0.5% S + 0.15% I	5810	5010
2860	2810			3880	3820
Benzene + 0.28% S	5842	5210	Benzene + 0.5% S + 0.15% I + FeCl ₃ (10% aqueous solution) 20%	5700	5012
	3700	3620			3920
Benzene + 0.52% S	5790	5240	Benzene + .5% S + .1% I + KCl (10% aqueous solution) 15%	2890	2830
	3780	3910			4510
Benzene + 1.2% S	5770	5260		3980	3860
	3800	3960		2840	2800
Benzene + 0.1% I	5800	5220			
	3980	3920			

D I S C U S S I O N

The strength of the bonds in the benzene complexes is indeed small, so that the absorption of light in the red region of the spectrum easily brings about their dissociation. For benzene and 0.10% of I₂, λ less than 5800Å brings about the rupture of the bonds

between the constituents of the complexes. This leads to a value of the heat of dissociation equal to R , where

$$R = \frac{N h \nu}{J} = \frac{286,000}{\lambda(\text{\AA})} = 49.31 \text{ kilo-calories.}$$

Here h is Planck's constant, N is Avogadro's number, ν , the frequency of the quanta and J , the Joule's equivalent. The retransmitted patch below $5220\text{\AA}$ shows that the absorption of light above the corresponding frequency, not only dissociates the complex, but also raises iodine normal or ionised to higher states of electronic excitation. Such a phenomenon is met with in the case of photodissociation of diatomic molecules. The photodissociation at $\lambda 5800\text{\AA}$ disrupts the constituents into normal states, while the photodissociation at $3980\text{\AA}$ after breaking asunder the complex raises the constituents, one or both to higher excited states and these ruptured parts then fly apart with the balance of energy shared as kinetic energy between them. The difference of frequency corresponding to the shift of the position of absorption from $\nu 25125$ to 17241 cm^{-1} comes out to be 7884 cm^{-1} , while the frequency difference for the states $6d^2D_1$ and $6d^2D_2$ of I^+ is 8372 cm^{-1} . The agreement between these values is nice, and it involves a forbidden transition. The phenomenon of the collision of the first and the second kind, as well as the regular and forbidden transitions play a significant rôle in the thermal or photochemical dissociation of these complexes which become heavier on further addition of S, I, FeCl₂ or KCl.

Coming to the sulphur complexes of benzene, we find that the dissociation begins at $5840\text{\AA}$. Hence the heat of dissociation is $48.96 \text{ K. calories}$. The frequency difference between the two important edges of this complex is $27027 - 19194 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ i.e., 7833 cm^{-1} and a second difference is $27624 - 19194 = 8430 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. These differences agree well with $\nu = 9672 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, involving the transition $3s^2 3p^2 D_{3/2}$ and $3s^2 3p^2 P_{3/2}$ of S^+ , showing that the nature of these complexes is ionic in character and Kratzer's theory of the dissociation of diatomic molecules as modified by Born and Frank (*Z. Physik*, 1925, 31, 1411) may be applicable to the photodissociation of these complexes.

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